

EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
of Coastal Communities

Policy Brief An Equitable Ocean Pact?

Leaving No One Behind in Just Coastal Community Transitions

The need to reflexively negotiate leaving no people(s), places, livelihoods and ecologies behind for coastal community resilience, wellbeing and just transitions.

The Ocean Pact stresses the importance of promoting a thriving and resilient blue economy that supports the well-being of people living in coastal communities while protecting ocean environments. Equity and Leaving No One Behind (LNOB) arguably have direct implications for the Ocean Pacts' capacity to better support thriving and resilient coastal communities.

The Green Deal emphasises the importance of LNOB as a just *'transition can only succeed if it is conducted in a fair and inclusive way. The most vulnerable are the most exposed to the harmful effects of climate change and environmental degradation'* (European Commission, 2019, p.16). However, what is meant by Leaving No One Behind in coastal community contexts is ambiguous and remains undefined.

Based on experiences from the **EmpowerUs project**, in which we actioned the LNOB principle in six Transition Coastal Labs (Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Ireland, Norway and Spain), we have explored the specific ways to understand and operationalise LNOB, highlighting multiple forms of coastal communities' transitions and what they grapple with.

The experience of actioning the LNOB principle in EmpowerUs was recorded through reflection interviews conducted with leaders of the Transition Coastal Labs. The analysis reveals multiple forms and interpretations of One in 'Leaving No One Behind' (see Table) – uncovering different ideas of equity – and highlighting tensions, trade-offs and the need to negotiate and balance perspectives within and among different LNOB forms. Balancing LNOB and striving for equity in coastal community transition arguably underpins the resilience and wellbeing of coastal communities, with direct importance to the Ocean Pact's comprehensive strategy.

We find that to Leave No One Behind means decision-makers need to attend to specific local contexts, relationships, and political processes. These are shaped by power dynamics at multiple levels and directly influence who participates, who benefits, and who or what risks being left behind.

Leave No One Behind	
Leave No <u>People(s)</u> Behind	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Context matters• Recognitional justice• Procedural justice• Distributional justice
Leave No <u>Place</u> Behind	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Marginalised geographies
Leave No <u>Livelihood</u> Behind	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Climate change• Livelihood conflicts in coastal development

Leave No One Behind

Leave No Ecologies Behind

- Neglected ecologies in coastal development
- Human impacts on ecologies
- Need to protect ecologies
- Creating sustainable ecological relations

Leaving No 'People(s)' Behind

Understanding 'One' as **people(s)** includes the emphasis on diverse individuals and social groups. The main takeaways from this understanding of LNOB are that:

1. Historical and present contexts create unique challenges and opportunities for the inclusion of people. Striving to include everyone may be difficult or even unrealistic, and sensitive decisions may be needed to prevent conflict, particularly when social groups carry histories of tension or division.
2. Identifying who is vulnerable or marginalised depends on the specific context and cannot be pre-defined (*Recognitional Justice*).
3. To facilitate the inclusion of social groups and the most vulnerable, there are specific procedural challenges and requirements that need to be negotiated and balanced (*Procedural Justice*), such as: using multiple approaches and methods; creating different channels for people to voice their opinions; engaging without ostracising; recognising that the most vulnerable might already be overburdened.
4. Leaving no people behind means not only ensuring participation in the process but also fair access to the outcomes and benefits (*Distributional Justice*). This requires prioritising who benefits from interventions, ethically negotiating who will benefit and in what ways.

Cyprus' history of war and displacement means ethnic divides need to be sensitively navigated to facilitate inclusion. Including everyone in the same process be very challenging and ethical negotiations are necessary. Yet it is important to ensure diverse group of people benefits from the outcome of projects.

Leaving no 'Place' Behind

Our analysis further reveals the understanding of LNOB as leaving no **place** behind. The European Commission has long recognised the need to focus on marginalised and deprived places and geographies. Equity across geographies means ensuring that no community should be disadvantaged because of its geography – which includes, for example, remote regions and islands and language minority regions such as our TCL in Connemara and the Aran Islands, Ireland.

In Connemara, Ireland, an ASSETS manual was developed to guide and support the social economy in the Irish-speaking Gaeltacht region. By supporting community owned businesses, it contributes to capturing place-based benefits from growth in the blue economy.

On Træna in Norway, the local strategy “*Hooked on Træna*” was developed to strengthen community cohesion across several physically dispersed islands. The initiative engages the community in creating and sharing place-based knowledge, local development, and cultural heritage.

Coastal areas face pressures such as rising seas, ecosystem degradation, and declining traditional industries, but also host opportunities for blue growth. While blue growth can generate jobs, foster innovation and resilience, it also risks sidelining smaller, remote or island communities. Applying a ‘no place left behind’ lens means aligning blue growth with inclusive governance and fair distribution of benefits across diverse coastal geographies, which can support their resilience and wellbeing in the long term.

Leaving no ‘Livelihood’ Behind

In the case of coastal communities, Leaving No One Behind can also refer to specific livelihoods, including traditional livelihoods such as small-scale fisheries, in the development of the blue economy. Leaving **livelihoods** behind is not just concerned with economic loss and struggles but is also a matter of loss of identity and cultural heritage – as well as the associated sense of place.

Recreational fisheries and aquaculture may suppress, and have stronger and more articulated voices than local, small-scale fisheries (e.g. Åland, Finland and Træna, Norway).

For example, in Cap de Creus, Spain, artisanal fishers have been losing access to traditional fishing due to privatisation and regulations favouring other livelihoods and sectors. Historically shared (communal) spaces, and fishing zones, are restricted or converted for tourism and conservation, excluding local communities.

Salt pans in Bulgaria are being damaged by climate change, causing for example flooding and decreased water salinity after heavy rainfall.

Coastal livelihoods are under threat for several reasons. Climate change causes rising temperatures, extreme weather, and ecosystem degradation that affect traditional uses of waters and the coastal resources, in turn affecting the ability to sustain livelihoods. Competing development pressures such as tourism, conservation policies and privatisation may displace or deprioritise livelihoods. These overlapping pressures create inequalities and disrupt cultural practices that have often sustained coastal community economy and environment over time.

Leaving no 'Ecologies' Behind

While LNOB often takes an anthropocentric worldview, our analysis further points to the need to leave no ecologies behind. This includes ecosystems, species, habitats and strengthening nature-people relations through nature-connectedness.

Coastal development, blue sectors and livelihood practices impact local ecologies, highlighting the tensions between leaving no ecologies behind versus leaving no livelihoods or people(s) behind.

In Burgas, Bulgaria, road infrastructure once walled off neighbourhoods from nearby lakes. The TCL strategy offers increasing nature-connectedness through developing access to water landscapes through biking paths and trails.

We also identify a need to strengthen people's connection and sense of belonging to local nature(s) and ecologies, which in turn builds ownership and responsibility. Interrelatedly, we find that there is a need to strengthen the relationship between humans and ecosystems: developing a sense of place, local identity, and understanding of marine resources, cultural heritage, and ecology as deeply intertwined, supporting collective action toward more sustainable solutions.

Negotiating Leaving No One Behind

Our framework for understanding LNOB presents many ethical, practical, and value-based tensions, trade-offs and dilemmas. LNOB often appears as a technical fix but, instead, there is a need to reflexively negotiate, navigate and balance perspectives of LNOB to strive for equitable coastal community transitions. In doing so, we observed a number of key aspects to consider:

- There are tensions between process (recognitional and procedural justice) and outcome (distributional justice);
- There are tensions between LN 'people(s)' B in a process and 'stakeholder fatigue';
- Method triangulation is important to involve diverse stakeholders, requiring flexibility in the project's design and room for reflexivity;
- Participation of some people(s) may risk the participation of other groups and therefore there is sometimes the need to leave some people(s) behind to not cause conflict;
- Focusing on leaving no place behind risks not paying attention to some 'peoples(s)' within the place;
- There are tensions between livelihoods and ecologies;
- There are intersecting dimensions of LNOB that include both humans and ecosystems that need to be addressed.

Conclusion & Recommendations

The Ocean Pact highlights the importance of supporting the well-being and resilience of coastal communities while developing a thriving blue economy that also protects the oceans. In this policy brief, we have integrated the Ocean Pact with the Green Deal and its emphasis on just transitions. We have done so by presenting a framework for understanding and operationalising Leaving No One Behind in coastal community transition developed through experiences gained from working with LNOB in practice.

Our framework highlights a number of key aspects to consider when striving to build coastal community well-being and resilience as is prioritised in the Ocean Pact. We recommend the following:

- It is important to include diverse individuals and social groups (e.g. gender, indigenous groups and youth) in order to develop resilient coastal communities and to enhance community wellbeing. To **leave no people(s) behind** means decision-makers need to consider local contexts, recognitional, procedural and distributive justice.
- There is a need to focus on and prioritise marginalised geographies (i.e. **leave no place behind**) in blue economies – making sure that coastal communities can capture benefits coming out of blue growth.
- Focusing on **leaving no livelihood behind** is key to ensuring an equitable coastal transition that also supports cultural heritage, local identities and community practices that underpin community wellbeing and resilience.
- To leave no one behind also means **leaving no ecologies behind**. Our framework highlights the need to shift perspectives toward seeing humans as part of ecological systems – creating sustainable relationships that mean neither human nor ecologies are left behind.
- Leaving No One Behind is not a technical fix that can ensure equity in coastal community transitions. There is a need to **reflexively, ethically and practically negotiate different forms of Leaving No One Behind** when striving for equitable coastal community transitions.

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